

Review

IoT sensors for remote patient monitoring

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Abstract: One of the sectors where the Internet of Things (IoT) technology has chosen to live is healthcare. Indeed, using this revolutionary paradigm known as IoT, a variety of platforms are being built to bring patients closer to doctors. Most patients experience mobility issues across the world, and this phenomena of IoT-based health monitoring has allowed these patients to obtain healthcare without having to attend a health center. The overall goal of IoT monitoring in healthcare is to bring patients and doctors closer together. As a result, a wide range of medical sensors and other IoT components are utilized to remotely monitor medical indicators, including body temperature, body position, blood glucose level, heart rate, and blood pressure. Sensor advancements, wireless connectivity, and data processing technologies are unquestionably driving forces for data processing. This article will provide an overview of the IoT ecosystem in the field of e-health, as well as the importance of IoT Sensors for Remote Patient Monitoring and different types of IoT Sensors for Remote Patient Monitoring, such as heartbeat sensors, temperature sensors, blood pressure sensors, blood glucose sensors, and electromyography sensors.

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Introduction

Everyone should be able to live a long and healthy life in any place on the planet. The number of persons aged 60 and up is growing, as is their share in the population. According to WHO one billion persons aged 60 and up were alive in 2019. By 2030, the population will be 1.4 billion, and by 2050, it will be 2.1 billion [17]. This rise is occurring at an unprecedented rate and is expected to intensify in the future decades, especially in emerging nations. Since its inception in 1999 by Kevin Ashton, the Internet of Things has grown and spread its tentacles across almost every facet of human existence [1]. The Internet of Things (IoT) was created to make many aspects of life easier, including healthcare, especially for individuals who are unable to travel to a hospital to see a doctor due to financial constraints or distance. In the recent decade, the Internet of Things (IoT) has made any thing intrinsically linked, and it has been hailed as the next technological revolution. This new form of information and communication technology which is referred to as the internet of things (IoT) is very crucial in the field of healthcare [2]. Health data is collected via sensors affixed to the patient's body. The data is subsequently sent to a remote server on the healthcare facility's grounds over a cellular network such as 3G/4G, general packet radio service (GPRS), high-speed packet access (HSPA), or Long-Term

Evolution (LTE) [3]. The primary objective of this research review is to highlight the many sensors that are used to collect health data from patients and transfer that data to a doctor in another part of the world for medical assistance. An overview of the IoT ecosystem in the field of e-health is illustrated in figure 1 below.

Fig. 1: An overview of the IoT ecosystem in the field of e-health [18]

The Importance of IoT Sensors for Remote Patient Monitoring

According to a World Health Organization estimate, around 44% of member states have less than one physician per thousand people [4] as cited in [2]. As a result, it's critical to create a system that allows people to consult physicians from the comfort of their own homes for medical advice. This can only be done with the aid of sensors attached to patients to detect medical irregularities. These sensors may be used to collect healthcare data and communicate it to remote medical institutes. The Internet of Things has been used to monitor patients, follow everyday activities, and care for the elderly via wearable biosensors. It is possible to expect that the Internet of Things, when combined with sophisticated clinical sensors, would significantly increase personal pleasure while also preventing the occurrence of medical disorders. In reality, low-cost medical sensors can be wirelessly connected to other devices in the IoT, making it possible to construct implanted sensors to monitor patients' health problems.

IoT Sensor types for Remote Patient Monitoring

There are a wide range of IoT sensors used by health practitioners for remotely monitoring patient's health over the internet. These sensors are electronically designed to sense specified health parameters of patients and then transmits the result through microcontrollers and gateways to monitoring software located at the premises of the physician for medical intervention. These sensors are worn by the patients and they gather information such as blood level, sugar level, weight, heart rate, blood pressure etc. The purpose of this article is to bring to the limelight the var-

ious sensors used for collecting health data from patients body for onward transmission to a doctor on the other part of the world through the internet.

Heartbeat Sensor

There are many different types of heartbeat sensors on the market today, but they all serve the same purpose: to capture the heartbeats of patients. The heart rate is measured using the Heart Beat sensor, which is worn on the fingertip of the patient. This Heart Beat Sensor has to be connected to a microcontroller such as an Arduino or Raspberry Pi for data processing and transmission. A heartbeat sensor is presented in [5]. Here, when the patient's heart beats, blood is pumped into the artery on the tip of the finger. This creates a shift in blood volume, which is detected by the heartbeat sensor. To measure this change in blood flow, the sensor employed an infrared light source on one side of the finger and a photo detector on the other. The intensity of light followed on the photo diode fluctuates as the blood flow changes, and the onboard equipment generates a PPG waveform. This PPG waveform is timed to the heartbeat. Another heartbeat sensor is presented in [6] consisting of a sensor and a control circuit, as shown in Figure 3 below. An IR LED and a photo diode put in a clip make up the sensor element of the Heartbeat Sensor. An Op-Amp IC and a few other components make up the control circuit, which is used to link the signal to the microcontroller. The pulses are detected using the finger-type heartbeat sensor. The volume of blood in the finger varies with each heartbeat, as does the light from the IR LED traveling through the finger and being detected by the photo diode. According to [7] the heart rate is monitored using a pair of LEDs and LDRs, as well as a microprocessor, and it is based on optoelectronics fundamental. The IR led emits infrared radiation, which is reflected by the surface. The amount of radiation produced an electron-hole pair, which resulted in leakage current. The proportional voltage is obtained by passing this current via a resistor. As a result, the higher the intensity of the incoming ray, the higher the voltage flowing across the resistor.

Fig. 2: Heartbeat Sensor [5]

Fig. 3: Heartbeat Sensor [6]

Temperature Sensor

A temperature sensor can determine the temperature of a person either by coming into contact with the person or by detecting infrared radiation generated by the person from a distance. According to [7], the temperature of a patient can be remotely monitored using an LM35 sensor, which is an IC sensor with an analog output proportional to the instantaneous temperature. The LM35 is an IC temperature sensor with a proportional output voltage to Celsius temperature. The LM35 is advantageous than linear temperature sensors with Kelvin calibration because it does not need subtracting a huge constant voltage from the output value to get a Celsius reading. The LM35 sensor's distinguishing qualities make connecting with any type of circuit a pleasure. The LM35 sensor works on the fundamental idea of a diode, in which the voltage across a diode increases at a predictable pace as the temperature rises. It's simple to make

Blood Glucose Sensor

Blood sugar, often known as glucose, is the most common sugar present in the body. It is your body's major source of energy and comes from the food you eat. Your blood transports glucose to all of your body's cells, where it is used for energy. Diabetes is a disorder in which your blood sugar levels are excessively high, and having too much glucose in your blood can lead to significant complications over time [13]. Even if you don't have diabetes, you may occasionally experience issues with low blood sugar (trembling, headache, weakness, feeling mentally sluggish, heart palpitations, blurred sight and tingling lips) [14]. As a result, it's critical to keep track of these variables in order to maintain a consistent food, exercise, and medication regimen. IoT sensors can be used to remotely monitor a patient's blood pressure.

Fig. 8: Low blood sugar [14]

Fig. 9: High blood sugar
(Pittawut)

Fig. 10: Blood glucose remote sensor [15]

Electromyography Sensor

An EMG sensor, also known as an electromyography sensor, detects little electrical impulses produced by your muscles as you move them. This includes actions as easy as raising your arm, tightening your fist, or wiggling a finger [16]. EMG sensors are frequently employed in biological applications, such as supporting doctors in the diagnosis and treatment of patients with muscle and nerve issues. This signal is used to operate prosthetic devices like hands, arms, and lower limbs.

Fig. 11: Electormyography sensor for remote monitoring [16]

Conclusions

Remote patient monitoring (RPM) has a number of advantages for doctors, including easier access to patient data, the opportunity to give higher-quality treatment to more patients while reducing burnout, and cheaper costs and improved efficiency for healthcare providers, to name a few. The purpose of this article was to highlight the many sensors that are used to collect health data from patients and transfer that data to a doctor in another part of the world for medical assistance. As a result, this article covered the IoT ecosystem in the field of e-health, as well as the importance of IoT Sensors for Remote Patient Monitoring and the various types of IoT Sensors for Remote Patient Monitoring, such as heartbeat sensors, temperature sensors, blood pressure sensors, blood glucose sensors, and electromyography sensors.

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